

Interact @RASOP: Traceability project. Part 1.

Name: _____ email: _____

Session instructions:

This workshop consists of one task: **Manually discovering the traceability links between a set of user stories and an EDG.** Since this is a graded workshop (**3% of the final grade**), you must develop it individually! **Talking, chatting, and sending emails are not allowed during the workshop.** Read first all the instructions before start.

Follow the next steps to complete the workshop:

- 1) Access to Moodle's activity titled: "Traceability project part 1."
- 2) Download the "Traceability-project-part1.drawio" file, and the Excel file "Traceability-matrix.xlsx"
- 3) Open the file "Traceability-project-part1.drawio" using the draw.io application in windows or using your browser in "diagrams.net".
- 4) Please write down now your starting time

Starting time (HH:MM): _____

- 5) Read the user stories.
- 6) Read the Existence Dependency Graph (EDG).
- 7) Discover all the traces between the user stories and the EDG. Report them in the Excel file "Traceability-matrix.xlsx" using the convention exemplified below:

Identifier of Source Artifact	Identifier of Target Artifact
S1002	T920
S1002	T930
S4002	T402
S4002	T920

Create one trace link (a link from Source To -Target) per row using the identifiers provided in the "Traceability-project-part1.drawio" file. Each artifact can appear several times, just one time, or not appearing at all. For instance, in our previous table, there is a trace link between the source artefact S1002 and the target artifact T920. You can create several trace links.

Remember, the important thing about this workshop is **NOT** that **ALL** the artifacts have a trace link, but you be **ACCURATE** on the trace links you discover. Please let the lecturers know if you have any problems, questions, or comments during the workshop!

- 8) When you think there are no more trace links between user stories and the EDG to discover, save your solutions written on your Excel file. Then, write down your ending time:
Ending time (HH:MM): _____
- 9) Upload the Excel file with your solutions via Moodle.

10) Fill in the following questionnaire:

G1	How much do you agree with the following statements? Mark with an X your agreement level, having: (1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree; (3) Nor disagree nor agree, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree					
	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
	Using a manual traceability strategy , I easily traced user stories into the EDG.					
	Tracing user stories into the EDG is an understandable process using a manual traceability strategy .					
	I found that the manual traceability strategy generally helps trace user stories into the EDG.					
	It seemed to me that tracing user stories into the EDG using a manual traceability strategy is a straightforward process.					
	I am sure that I have the needed abilities to trace user stories into the EDG.					
	I think the effort to trace the user stories to the EDG using a manual traceability strategy is low.					
	In general, it is easy to understand how to trace user stories to EDG by using a manual traceability strategy .					
	I could explain how to trace user stories into the EDG to another person that does not know the manual traceability strategy .					
	Using a manual traceability strategy , I think it is easy to trace user stories into the EDG					
	I think the using a manual traceability strategy is an effective solution for tracing user stories into EDG.					
	I can efficiently trace user stories into the EDG by using a manual traceability strategy .					
	I think the manual traceability strategy for tracing user stories into EDG is the best way to do it.					
	Definitely, I will use a manual traceability strategy for tracing user stories into the EDG.					
	I prefer to use a manual traceability strategy for tracing user stories into the EDG.					

11) When you finish uploading the file, and have filled the questionnaire, deliver the documents to one of the lecturers, they will check if everything is OK.